
Exploring Innovation and ISO Standard Improvement in Health Care Micro-systems in Mauritius: A Cross-Case Analysis

Gilbert Roland

RN, BSc (Hons), MPH.

Port Louis, Mauritius; Email: Groland642@gmail.com

Dr. Jane Marry Gill

Associate Professor – Pinehill University

North Carolina, United States of America

Abstract

One of the key areas of consideration in the healthcare organisation is the management of quality. The management of the quality in the healthcare sector is dependent on numerous factors such as patient satisfaction, innovation and improvement in the ISO standard. The predefined aim of this research was to explore the impact of innovation and ISO standard improvement on the satisfaction of the patients and overall quality of the healthcare organisations. In addition, this research paper also highlights the introduction and adaptability of changing trends and modern technologies. The cross-case analysis of the health care micro-systems in Mauritius was used to explore the innovation and ISO standard improvement, the satisfaction of patient, and the overall impact of these factors on the improvement of quality. This cross-case analysis was carried out using the mixed methodological procedure. Thus, quantitative and qualitative techniques were used for collection of numerical data as well as exploring the perception of different participants. For the quantitative part of the research, the sample size was 1850 while for qualitative part, the sample size was 10. The quantitative data were collected by using survey questionnaire and analysed by the SPSS. On the other hand, the qualitative data was collected through semi-structured interviews with the participants and was scrutinised by using thematic analysis approach. The outcomes of this research declared that overall quality of the health care system can be improved by improving the satisfaction of the patients, ISO compliance, and adaptability of innovation and changes in the information technology.

Keywords: *Cross-case analysis, Health Care Micro-systems, mixed methods, patient satisfaction, Innovation., Mauritius healthcare sector, ISO Standard Improvement.*

1. Introduction

In healthcare organisations, the quality was described as the improvement in the clinical services to patients and decrease mortality rates. The quality measures in the healthcare system are related to satisfaction of patient and use of standard procedures for the diagnosis and treatment of the patients. In addition, quality measurement is also analysed by determination of procedures that are followed by healthcare professionals [1]. Furthermore, the quality of processes in the healthcare organisations must also be improved by following efficiency improvement protocol [2]. New technologies are used by the health care system to improve their quality and also enhancing the efficiency of different processes in the organisations. The quality measurement of any healthcare organisation is dependent on different factors such as innovation, adoption of technology, patient satisfaction, work efficiency, and following ISO standards for healthcare organisations [3]. Another factor that can improve quality measurement of the health sector is active involvement of different healthcare professionals in the implementation of different standard procedures.

The healthcare sector of Mauritius is less developed as compared to other healthcare systems. Based on the ranking of quality of healthcare services of the World Health Organization Mauritius comes on 84th rank [4]. The lack of funds, resources, and implementation of ISO standards is the reason for different issues that are faced by this healthcare sector. The quality of services delivered to patients can be improved by the use of information technology and innovation. Different healthcare organisations have implemented innovation, information technology, and ISO standards for improving the processes of quality management and overall efficiency of healthcare sector [5]. The predefined aim of this research is the analysis of the quality measurement

processes for bringing improvement in the organisations. The focus of this research is to determine the relationship between quality measurement and improvements in innovation and adaptability of information technology in the healthcare micro-systems of Mauritius. Another focus of this research is to explore perceptions of healthcare executives and patients regarding the efficiency of procedures used in the healthcare sector.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Quality Management in the Healthcare Micro-Systems

The healthcare organisations are tended to provide quality care services to the service users to avoid medical complications. The employees working in health care sector are associated with the use of strategies that can lead to satisfaction of the service users [6]. This was the reason why quality management was used to improve the effectiveness of services. Quality management is based on the management procedures and the researchers have demonstrated that technology advancements and innovation can bring competitive advancements to the organisations [7].

The quality of services can also be improved by the integration of ISO standards, technological advancements, and innovation. The healthcare organisations are now using the ISO certification programs for improving the organisational performance. Quality management is the method used for managing organisations and the main aim of the quality management is to bring improvements in the healthcare system along with providing high-quality patient care. Quality management is the most crucial factor to provide high-quality services to the patient and achieve their satisfaction [8]. Therefore, the implementation of the quality management processes is imperative within the health organisations. In this regard, the active involvement of health care professionals and higher authorities is required.

ISO standards applied to quality management can improve the quality of healthcare services. The organisational management is required to analyse the specificities of organisational culture, quality of health services, and different organisational procedures with compliance to ISO standards [9].

2.2 Innovation and Information Technology in the Healthcare Micro-Systems

The technological advancement and innovation within the healthcare sector have improved the processes to a great level [10]. These advancements have improved the quality of services provided to the patients. The use of innovation and technology has also improved the healthcare management within the healthcare

organisations as well as the quality of the services provided to the patients. The use of technology within the healthcare sector maintain the quality inspection [11]. The innovation and information technology is responsible to make the organisational management effective to use the available resources in an appropriate manner. Health sector organisations are adopting these processes to improve well-being and health of service users [12]. Furthermore, the healthcare organisations use the information technology and innovation for analysing current quality standards and standard of the organisation.

2.3 ISO Systems in Health Care

ISO bring improvement in effectiveness in compliance to clinical autonomy leading to the continuous improvement of services. ISO-9001 is also productive and effective. The implementation of ISO standard and Cloud technology does not always present the desired effect in health organisations, making it imperative to analyse the specificities of health quality, hospital organisational culture, and interaction of these characteristics with the ISO standard [13].

The implementation of systems of quality management, through standards such as ISO 9001, in organisations is a complex process. It is essential to consider the organisational culture, the operational, organisational objectives and the internal powers and not limit the quality to its instrumental aspects. But the failures of implementing quality programs in health organisations are not only due to poor organisational analysis, but also to product specificity (health care) and client satisfaction [14]. In order to understand the implementation of the ISO 9001 standard, the perception of the nurses and other healthcare professionals must be considered. In the new version of the ISO 9000 series, the following principles of quality management are inherent, based on Deming's teachings: customer focus; leadership; Involvement of people; Process approach; Systemic approach; Continuous improvement; Making based on facts; And relationships with suppliers for mutual benefit. However, to plan a coherent strategy for quality in a health organisation through the ISO standard, it is critical that communication on key concepts is accurate. Each organisation must know its professionals and the definition they have of quality [15].

For the health organisation to meet the current requirements, it is fundamental to develop continuous improvement, being one of the assumptions for the certification of quality systems, according to ISO 9000: 2000 series standard. Standardization as the basis for quality of health arises from the need to provide objective evidence that quality has been achieved, as stated by Riskin *et al.* (2015) [16] an organisation cannot expect full customer satisfaction and react to competitiveness if it does not have the minimum requirements for quality

assurance. The ISO standard is the requirements of the quality systems, reaching only the operationalization of the concept of quality, pretending to be, as referred to by Carayon *et al.* (2014) [17], a set of specifications and characteristics of a product or service related to its capacity to meet the needs, which are known and presupposed. Thus, the standard should not be seen as an end in itself, is only a means to quality.

For this reason, the processes of efficiency improvement are dependent on a range of factors. For instance, the research conducted by Khanassov *et al.* [9] demonstrated that quality and efficiency improvement in healthcare organisations include the combination of technical, scientific, material, and human characteristics. Efficiency improvement also consists of the efficiency levels of workforce associated with the healthcare organisation. The quality of services delivered through the platform of healthcare organisations is also dependent on the expectations of service users. For instance, service users admitted in private healthcare sector normally tend to possess high levels of expectations, as compared to other patients [9]. The healthcare organisations need to improve the quality of their services within a certain budget; therefore, hospital management might fail to improve the efficiency of their services by considering a certain budget. Likewise, efficiency improvement is also dependent on the expertise levels of healthcare professionals employed in a healthcare organisation. The healthcare organisations are responsible for arranging training opportunities for their employees; however, lacking in the provision of training opportunities is anticipated to have a reduced efficiency of healthcare services.

On other hand, the research conducted by Goetsch *et al.* [15] demonstrated efficiency in terms of the use of information and resources for making important decisions. Efficiency was also discussed in terms of the provision of better quality service, by considering minimum cost. Similarly, the research conducted by Ogrinc *et al.* [5] stated that efficiency improvement processes in healthcare organisation need to involve processes related to supply, demands, quality of processes, impacts of services and patients' outcomes.

3. Research Methodology

For this investigation, the researchers have selected the mixed methodological approach. The reason for considering such approach was to get both qualitative and quantitative data for analysis. For the quantitative data collection survey through questionnaire was used while for qualitative data collection, semi-structured interview analysis approach is used. Furthermore, in this research, quantitative and qualitative triangulation was projected for carrying out robust analysis of data collected from

both approaches [18]. To increase validity and trustworthiness of the research, it was important to consider primary and secondary information too.

The information collectively increased the validity of outcomes obtained from the research. In this research, a qualitative approach is used for conducting an analysis of the views, concepts, ideas and perceptions of the patients, visiting health care sector and health care providers, working to provide care services to the patients. In addition, the qualitative part of this research was focused on maintaining anonymity, privacy, and confidentiality of participants of research. On the other hand, quantitative approach was used in this research for the collection and analysis of quantitative numerical data with the aid of statistical tools. In comparison to the qualitative method, the quantitative methodology is a reliable method used for research [19]. As both the qualitative and quantitative approaches have advantages; and therefore, the researchers have used mixed research methodology for collection of extensive data that can provide detailed and reliable outcomes for this research.

3.1. Hypotheses

As the aim of this research was to evaluate the impact of adapting innovation and bringing improvement in ISO standards, therefore, the hypothesis were developed to evaluate the impact. The evaluation of satisfaction level of patient and quality of health care processes is carried out for testing ISO compliance and adaptability of innovation. The questionnaires for the collection of quantitative and qualitative data were developed to test these hypothesis and questions were also designed by considering all aspects. The researcher considered following hypotheses.

H1: There is no difference between the patients' satisfaction and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

H2: There is no difference in the ISO compliance and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

H3: There is no difference between adaptability and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

4. Research Setting

The setting for this research was some healthcare organisations that were located in the Republic of Mauritius to explore improvements in ISO Standard and innovation in its healthcare micro-systems. The healthcare professionals were physicians or medical doctors, dentists, nurse, pharmacist, and midwifery professionals.

Among health care organizations in the government sector, this research has considered that micro-level

healthcare organisation that had at least 100 beds for patients. In addition, few of these large hospitals that were included Victoria in Quatres Bornes, Dr Agarwal hospital, Sir Seewoosagur Ramgoolam National Hospital, and Apollo Bramwell.

5. Population and Sampling

The sample population for this research was comprised of, healthcare executives, board members of health care settings, and health administration managers. Additionally, health care professionals, who work in these health care organisations, were also participants of this research to take their response and perceptions. As the innovation and standard procedures that are used in the healthcare organisations affect the quality of services provided to the patients, thus, it was also important to take the perception of the patient regarding quality management, innovation, and standard followed in these organisations [20]. This was the reason that the patient visiting these health care organisations were also considered as participants in this research.

As this research was based on mixed methodology, therefore, it was comprised of quantitative and qualitative phase. Due to the use of two types of methods for collecting data, two types sample sizes were considered. For the quantitative phase, a total number of participants was 1850, while for the qualitative phase, a sample size of the current research was 10 participants. The sample size for the quantitative phase was estimated by the use of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), while for the qualitative phase, the sample size was calculated by using effect size 0.10 with a power of 0.80 and alpha value was set at 0.05 [21]. Among 1850 participants selected for quantitative research, 50 were excluded because 30 of them did not return questionnaire, while 20 of them unusable questionnaires as more than one options were selected for many questions or in some cases, only 3-4 questions were answered. After performing analysis, 1850 participants for quantitative; while 10 participants for qualitative phase were selected.

This research has used the stratified sampling approach for the participants selected for the quantitative phase of this research study. The reason of using stratified sampling approach is to deal with large sample size by grouping them into different subgroups. On contrary to this, sampling approach used for the qualitative part of the research was purposive sampling. The purposive sampling is related to theoretical consideration as well as analysis of data that is supportive of developing a theory. Thus, this sampling method is effective for the qualitative research, which is explorative in nature.

6. Data Collection Tools

The two methods used for data collection were semi-structured interviews and surveys. The semi-structured interviews are considered as an effective tool for the collection of descriptive data for the qualitative research. The qualitative research requires analysing the perceptions of the individuals regarding their concepts experiences and for this purpose, the use of semi-structured interview is a justified approach for this purpose. It is effective to acquire the perceptions and concepts of participants regarding any phenomenon. The semi-structured interview was carried out by using self-administered questionnaire [22]. Before collecting data from participants, a cover letter explaining aims and objectives of research and an informed consent was provided to all participants.

However, for the quantitative phase of research, a closed-end questionnaire was used. It was administered online and this survey was not required by visiting healthcare organisations [23]. A questionnaire designed for quantitative phase was designed on five point Likert scales ranged from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The reason for using close-ended questions is to maintain the direction of research.

7. Developing and Piloting the Data Collection Instruments

After designing the research question, it was pre-tested to find out whether the original research question adopted was applicable and could give the required outcome. For the pilot study, charts (N=50, Public Hospital N= 2, and Private Hospital N=1) were randomly picked from the registry of the hospitals had the same characteristics as required for the main study. During the pre-testing, questionnaires for the health care professionals were pre-tested for the possible problems regarding rejection or non-participation while administering questionnaire. The pre-testing was also to find out the reliability and feasibility of the items to address the research questions. The questionnaire was developed by closed-ended questions including five options ranging from 'significant disagree to significantly. Pre-testing helps to ensure that the data collecting instruments answer the questions posed for the study and again helps check and try the planned statistical analysis.

8. Reliability of Data Collection Tool

The Cronbach's alpha was calculated for the evaluation of the reliability of data collected from participants. The reason for using the statistical test was to measure the reliability of all the questions that were included in the questionnaire designed for the survey.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics Scale

Case Processing Summary			
		N	Percent
Cases	Valid	1750	97.22
	Excluded ^a	50	2.78
	Total	1800	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.63	67

The Cronbach's alpha value obtained for this research was 0.63, which indicates that the research questionnaire used for this research is reliable. This research has used reliability index that was used by Bonett and Wright [22]. According to Bonett and Wright, dimensions and items that are included in the questionnaire survey are psychometrically sound at the micro healthcare or hospital level.

Thus, considering reliability index assessment can be used for analysis of the efficiency of services that are provided in the healthcare system. Furthermore, the researcher has also assured the reliability of data collection tool that was used for qualitative research. The data collection tool used for qualitative research was informed by word quotes and verbatim. The focus group interview was carried out, and transcripts of interviews were recorded and coded. This has helped in developing thematic analysis for this research.

9. Transferability and Credibility of this Research

Due to limited financial resources and time constraints, only four very large hospitals were included in this research. However, research outcomes obtained from these hospitals have not affected the research outcomes. Thus, this research ensures transferability of research and results obtained from this research can be transferred to understand the other health care system in Mauritius.

On the other hand, the employees' recruitment is carried out by taking into consideration different managerial level and this assures credibility of research. Furthermore, names of participants and their certification regarding healthcare administration were confirmed before the selection of these participants for research.

10. Ethical Considerations

The ethical consideration is an integral part of research and to maintain the ethical integrity of this research, ethical approval was taken from the Institutional review board prior conducting research. Moreover, confidentiality of all participants was ensured to avoid

any type of harm. In addition, reciprocity of the participants was also managed. It was also assured that data is collected in a lawful and air manner. Furthermore, anonymity and confidentiality of data were maintained. Till the research was completed, the data achieved from the participants was kept safe. It was also assured by the researcher that data of the participants is protected and is not transferred or used.

11. Results and Findings

11.1 Quantitative Phase

11.1.1 Variables.

Table 2: Dependent and Independent Variables used for Research

Dependent Variable	
1.	Overall Quality of Health Care (QHC)
Independent Variable	
1.	Patients' Satisfactions (PS)
2.	ISO Quality Standards Compliance (ISO)
3.	Adaptability to revolution requirements (Adpt)

For this research, the dependent variable was the quality of health care system, while the dependent variable used for this research was the quality measurement and efficiency improvement of healthcare organisations are dependent on various factors. ISO quality standards and adaptability to revolution requirements were considered as independent variables for this research. The dependent and independent variables used for this research were coded by the use of initials for putting it in the statistical software.

11.1.2 Demographics.

As the number of the participants used for quantitative phase was large, thus, demographic information of these participants was also calculated. The key elements considered in the demographic information included gender, age, and qualification of the research participants. The basic reason for collection of demographic information was the impact of age on the attitude and experience of participants included in the research. The demographic details of all participants are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Demographic Statistics

Demographic Statistics				
		Age	Gender	Educational Level
		1= 25-30 years, 2=31-40 years; 3=41-50 years)		(1= 5 years, 2=7 years; 3=10 years)
N	Valid	1750	1750	1750
	Missing	50	50	50
Mean		2.93	2.68	1.27

Median	2.00	2.00	2.00
Mode	2	2	2
Std. Deviation	5.211	1.196	10.035
Variance	10.258	1.955	5.692

H1: There is no difference in the ISO compliance and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 6: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 QHC	3.00	1750	0.43	0.01
ISO	3.01	1750	0.45	0.01

The median age of the respondents was 2.93 for age, and mean value for gender was 2.68, and the mean value for educational qualification was 1.27. In a similar manner, a table represents the standard deviation values.

11.1.3 QHC in comparison to Patient's Satisfaction

H1: There is no difference between the patients' satisfaction and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 4: Paired Samples Statistics

Pair 1	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
QHC	3.00	1750	0.43	0.01
PS	3.03	1750	0.44	0.01

Table 4 demonstrates that the mean value for the QHC is 3.00. On the other hand, the mean value for the PS is 3.03. The table also shows that the standard deviation value for the QHC is 0.43 while the value for the PS is 0.44. A total number of the participants in this research was 1750 participants.

Table 5: Paired Samples Test

Pair 1	Paired Differences				t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference			
			Lower	Upper		
QHC - PS	-0.03	0.62	-0.06	0.00	-1.94	0.05

Base on the outcomes obtained from this research has concluded that there is a statistically significant difference between the QHC and PS. According to the results presented in table 5, the mean number for patient satisfaction was equal to the mean for the quality of healthcare. Based on the outcomes, it can be concluded that participants who showed a preference for PS principally experience a better quality of care. Thus, the satisfaction of the patients indicates the improvements in the quality of care services that are provided to patients.

11.1.4 QHC in comparison ISO

Table 6 has presented that the mean value for the QHC for the sample size 1750 (n=1750) was 3.00, while the mean value for the ISO standards was 3.00. The standard deviation values for the QHC and ISO were 0.43 and 0.45.

Table 7: Paired Samples Test

Pair 1	Paired Differences				t	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference			
			Lower	Upper		
QHC - ISO	-0.01	0.63	-0.04	0.02	-0.49	.020

Table 7 has presented that statistical significance between QHC and ISO. The mean value for ISO compliance was less than the mean value for the quality of healthcare. Based on the outcomes of this research, it can be concluded that the research participants who represented a preference for ISO standards had experience better quality of care.

11.1.5 QHC in comparison to Adap

H3: There is no difference between adaptability and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 8: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 QHC	3.00	1750	0.43	0.01
WE	3.01	1750	0.35	0.01

In the Paired Samples Statistics Box, the mean for the QHC is 3.0013. The mean for the Adap is 3.00. The standard deviation for the QHC is 0.43 and for the Adap, also 0.54. The number of participants in the sample (N) was 1750.

Table 9: Paired Sample Test

Pair 1	Paired Differences	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
--------	--------------------	---	-----------------

	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference			
			Lower	Upper		
QHC Adap	-0.00	0.69	-0.04	0.03	-0.03	0.03

Based on the outcomes of this hypothesis, it can conclude that there is a statistically significant difference between the QHC and Adaptability. The results have indicated that the Mean number for ISO compliance was less than the Mean for the quality of healthcare. It can conclude that participants who showed a preference for adaptability principally experience a better quality of care.

11.2 Qualitative Phase

The qualitative phase of the research is based on a collection of data on semi-structured interviews. After the semi-structured interviews, a thematic analysis method was used. Rubin and Babbie [23] stated the benefits of using of thematic analysis in the qualitative research. It is effective to determine the links between research objectives and research findings. The research participants were asked to provide their responses to the factors representing efficiency improvement within the healthcare organisation. The research participants employed at different management levels stated that efficiency of an organisation can be analysed in terms of the use of information technology.

In the qualitative phase of the research, the responses of managers, directors, health care employees and other professionals working in the health administration are collected. When the participants were asked about the development of standards of practices such as the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO), which provides guidance that;

“We just have started to work in this field and we have a plan about EHR but it is true that we don’t have enough workforce yet regarding telemedicine and e-health. Awareness about this matter is very much important for the health personnel as well as the patients.....private health sector can also take initiatives concerning this issue, as 60 percent of patients take health care services from private clinics and hospitals in Mauritius”.

(Participant 6)

Most of the participants mentioned that innovation and ISO improvements can lead to improvements in the healthcare systems in Mauritius. However, the prime challenge that occurs in the establishment of innovation is lack of diagnostic laboratory. Regarding the importance of the patients’ satisfaction in overall management of quality, one participant revealed that;

“Patients’ satisfaction is based on an affordable fee, promptness of attention, good staff attitude, respect for patients and their rights, providing privacy and confidentiality, providing adequate information, availability of drugs and logistics and above all a healthy and clean environment”.

(Participant 2)

One of the participants revealed the concepts of innovation and the improvements in the ISO standards as; *“The innovative use of health care technology would be different in different place and different situation. It does not have any standard definition. Different country has different infrastructure according to their economic condition, manpower and geographical structure. If anybody uses ISO for medical care whether it is store-forward or real-time; in that sense, we are doing telemedicine in Mauritius”.*

(Participant no. 4)

Regarding the adaptability of information technology and innovation, Manager Patient Safety and Quality presented his views as,

“Skills mismatch as left. Also the issue of the difficulty of time-poor staff having to interact with sluggish systems. The sense of IT systems replacing (not in a good way) skilled staff in some situations. Skill mix/experience in decision makers not ideal”.

(Participant no. 7)

When the participants were asked to describe the area of improvements for implementation of ISO standards and adaptability to innovation to enhance patient satisfaction, one of the clinical service managers described that;

“Need more personalised information provision/presentation and faster responsiveness in meeting their information needs ... need more consolidation/transformation of data to information and easy to use reporting tool”.

(Participant 8)

Regarding the innovation and adaptability of the information technology changes, the inadequacies to the implementation of ISO standards and innovation were explained by the Clinical Service Manager as;

“Lost savings and quality improvement opportunities.... Information too generic and not tailored enough to the context of need.... Inadequate clinical information vs. Finance and HR information”.

(Participant 1)

When the participants were asked to identify the areas of improvements regarding innovation, quality, and ISO standards, one of the participants revealed the current status of the sector as,

“Insufficient training. Need more super-users. Inadequate support including help desk.... Need more

consolidation/transformation of data to information and easy to use reporting tools”.

(Participant 5)

10. Discussion

This research study was focused on the exploration of improvements in innovation, patient satisfaction, adoption of information technology and innovation, and following ISO standards on the quality improvements in healthcare sectors. Three factors were considered to perform this research and these factors were patient satisfaction, ISO standards, and adaptability of technology. To evaluate the impact of these factors on the quality of healthcare system, the mixed methodological approach was implemented. Using both the quantitative and qualitative phases of this research provided significant outcomes for the research [16, 17]. As the data was collected by taking a large sample size for quantitative part of research and an appropriate size for semi-structured interviews, thus, outcomes obtained from this research can be generalised for all health care micro-systems in Mauritius.

Furthermore, this research was carried out by considering all people that can affect the overall quality of healthcare sector. The sample of this research included health care professionals providing care services, employees working in other disciplines of the health sector, and the patient. Therefore, this research is effective to acquire the perspectives of different people affecting the quality of health care system.

The reason for collecting data from healthcare professionals and service user was to perceive the concepts of both service providers and users regarding quality measurement. Furthermore, their perceptions and responses are used to describe the role of ISO standards and innovation in the quality measurement of health care micro-systems. Additionally, this research has analysed the quality measurement of health care systems in terms of the innovation, technology, ISO standards, and patients' satisfaction. The innovation and adoption of technology not only enhance the satisfaction level of the patient but also brings improvements in the standard of procedures followed in the organisation. The outcomes of this research were also justified by the outcomes of other research studies. For instance, the outcomes of research conducted by Schembri [24] revealed that adaptability of information technology and innovation is effective for monitoring quality of services that are provided to the patients.

The participants also described their perception about the factors affecting the quality of different activities in the healthcare organizations. The outcomes of the research have shown that to measure the quality of healthcare organizations, patient satisfaction is imperative.

Therefore, it is necessary to improve the quality of services and the healthcare professionals must improve their skills to enhance the satisfaction of patients. The innovations such as training of healthcare professionals and adoption of information technology for management of different organisational activities can be used to bring improvement in the quality. Based on the responses of the participants, it can also be demonstrated that innovation and information technology will enhance the interaction among different department and thus overall quality will be improved. These outcomes are also justified by the research study that was conducted by Bork-Hüffer [25].

This research has also revealed that quality measurement of health care micro-systems is also dependent on the innovation and use of technology. The healthcare system in Mauritius has been continuously moving towards improvement and this is demonstrated by the satisfaction level of patients, improvements in the implementation of ISO standards and adaptability of innovation and information technology. The critical analysis of outcomes obtained from this research has also revealed that some other factors affect the improvements and implementation of ISO standards and innovation. These factors are financial, political, and cultural factors of the healthcare systems. The challenges imposed by these factors can be improved by enhancing the expertise of healthcare professionals regarding the implementation of innovation, standard procedures, and technology. Further research studies regarding the implementation and evaluation of ISO standards and innovation considering the decrease in medical errors would be an effective approach.

11. Conclusion

This cross-case analysis of the micro-system in Mauritius has revealed that quality of care services provided by these healthcare organisations has been improving with the passage of time. This study has also demonstrated that the improvements in quality measurement implement in these healthcare sectors are the prime basis of efficiency improvements in healthcare systems. The reason behind this is that quality measurement has a strong link with the identification of elements that affect the efficiency of services provided to patients.

The improvements in the efficiency of the healthcare sector in Mauritius depends in the management and ISO standards improvements and innovation adaptability. The outcomes of this study revealed that most of the healthcare settings in Mauritius lack appropriate implementation of ISO standards due to lack of experienced and qualified professionals. The outcomes obtained for the effects of using ISO management standards in the healthcare organization in the quality measurement and efficiency of these systems described that organisations that have adopted ISO standards having

an overall improvement in their efficiency. Following the ISO standard improvement lead to integrated care to service users; however, the low interaction between different healthcare sectors affect the delivery of care services and thus overall, the efficiency of the health sector.

The determination of a quality measurement of healthcare organisation in terms of patient satisfaction demonstrated that overall quality has a significant relationship with the patient satisfaction. In case of high level of patient satisfaction, the quality of healthcare sector tends to improve. Another focus area of this research was also to determine the quality measurement in terms of implementation of innovation and information technology in the healthcare organisations of Mauritius. Based on outcomes, it can be concluded that healthcare sector of Mauritius is now using the information technology for the quality measurement. The overall efficiency of different healthcare sectors and quality of services are now improving due to the adoption of information technology. Thus, based on the outcomes, it can be declared that patient satisfaction, the implementation of ISO standards, and improvements in innovation and adaptability of information technology and innovation have a significant influence on the total quality measurement of the healthcare sector in Mauritius.

12. Acknowledgment

First of all, I would like to say thanks to God, who has provided me opportunities and skills to complete this task. Furthermore, I would like to pay special thanks to my supervisor for his guidance and support throughout the research. I also want to pay a gratitude to my parents, family, friends, and classmates for their support and suggestions throughout this research.

13. References

- [1]. Wiig, Siri, Glenn Robert, Janet E. Anderson, Elina Pietikainen, Teemu Reiman, Luigi Macchi, and Karina Aase. "Applying different quality and safety models in healthcare improvement work: Boundary objects and system
- [2]. Armony, Mor, Shlomo Israelit, Avishai Mandelbaum, Yariv N. Marmor, Yulia Tseytlin, and Galit B. Yom-Tov. "On patient flow in hospitals: A data-based queueing-science perspective." *Stochastic Systems* 5, no. 1 (2015): 146-194.
- [3]. World Health Organization. *World Health Statistics 2016: Monitoring Health for the SDGs Sustainable Development Goals*. World Health Organization, 2016.
- [4]. McPherson, Richard A., and Matthew R. Pincus. *Henry's Clinical Diagnosis and Management by Laboratory Methods E-Book*. Elsevier Health Sciences, 2017.
- [5]. Ogrinc, Greg, Louise Davies, Daisy Goodman, Paul Batalden, Frank Davidoff, and David Stevens. "SQUIRE 2.0 (Standards for Quality Improvement Reporting Excellence): revised publication guidelines from a detailed consensus process." *The Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing* 46, no. 11 (2015): 501-507. thinking. "Reliability Engineering & System Safety" 125 (2014): 134-144.
- [6]. Obermeyer, Ziad, Maggie Makar, Samer Abujaber, Francesca Dominici, Susan Block, and David M. Cutler. "Association between the Medicare hospice benefit and health care utilization and costs for patients with poor-prognosis cancer." *Jama* 312, no. 18 (2014): 1888-1896.
- [7]. Mitra, Amitava. *Fundamentals of quality control and improvement*. John Wiley & Sons, 2016.
- [8]. Yang, Ji-Jiang, Jianqiang Li, Jacob Mulder, Yongcai Wang, Shi Chen, Hong Wu, Qing Wang, and Hui Pan. "Emerging information technologies for enhanced healthcare." *Computers in Industry* 69 (2015): 3-11.
- [9]. Khanassov, Vladimir, Isabelle Vedel, and Pierre Pluye. "Case management for dementia in primary health care: a systematic mixed studies review based on the diffusion of innovation model." *Clinical interventions in aging* 9 (2014): 915.
- [10]. Sultan, Nabil. "Making use of cloud computing for healthcare provision: Opportunities and challenges." *International Journal of Information Management* 34, no. 2 (2014): 177-184.
- [11]. Wright, Brad, Amy MJ O'Shea, Justin M. Glasgow, Padmaja Ayyagari, and Mary Vaughan-Sarrazin. "Patient, hospital, and local health system characteristics associated with the use of observation stays in veterans health administration hospitals, 2005 to 2012." *Medicine* 95, no. 36 (2016).
- [12]. Davis Giardina, Traber, Shailaja Menon, Danielle E. Parrish, Dean F. Sittig, and Hardeep Singh. "Patient access to medical records and healthcare outcomes: a systematic review." *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 21, no. 4 (2013): 737-741.
- [13]. Armony, Mor, Shlomo Israelit, Avishai Mandelbaum, Yariv N. Marmor, Yulia Tseytlin, and Galit B. Yom-Tov. "On patient flow in

- hospitals: A data-based queueing-science perspective." *Stochastic Systems* 5, no. 1 (2015): 146-194.
- [14]. Weller, Jennifer, Matt Boyd, and David Cumin. "Teams, tribes and patient safety: overcoming barriers to effective teamwork in healthcare." *Postgraduate medical journal* 90, no. 1061 (2014): 149-154.
- [15]. Goetsch, David L., and Stanley B. Davis. *Quality management for organizational excellence*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson, 2014.
- [16]. Riskin L, Koppel R, Riskin D. Re-examining health IT policy: what will it take to derive value from our investment?. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*. 2014 Oct 17;22(2):459-64.
- [17]. Carayon, P., Wetterneck, T.B., Rivera-Rodriguez, A.J., Hundt, A.S., Hoonakker, P., Holden, R. and Gurses, A.P., 2014. Human factors systems approach to healthcare quality and patient safety. *Applied ergonomics*, 45(1), pp.14-25.
- [18]. Creswell, John W. *A concise introduction to mixed methods research*. Sage Publications, 2014.
- [19]. Creswell, John W., and Cheryl N. Poth. *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Sage publications, 2014.
- [20]. Tipton, Elizabeth, Larry Hedges, Michael Vaden-Kiernan, Geoffrey Borman, Kate Sullivan, and Sarah Caverly. "Sample selection in randomized experiments: A new method using propensity score stratified sampling." *Journal of Research on Educational Effectiveness* 7, no. 1 (2014): 114-135.
- [21]. Yüksel, Atila. "A critique of "Response Bias" in the tourism, travel and hospitality research." *Tourism Management* 59 (2017): 376-384.
- [22]. Bonett, Douglas G., and Thomas A. Wright. "Cronbach's alpha reliability: Interval estimation, hypothesis testing, and sample size planning." *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 36, no. 1 (2015): 3-15.
- [23]. Rubin, Allen, and Earl R. Babbie. *Empowerment series: Research methods for social work*. Cengage Learning, 2016.
- [24]. Schembri, Sharon. "Experiencing health care service quality: through patients' eyes." *Australian Health Review* 39, no. 1 (2015): 109-116.
- [25]. Bork-Hüffer, Tabea. "Healthcare-Seeking Practices of African and Rural-to-Urban Migrants in Guangzhou." *Journal of Current Chinese Affairs* 44, no. 4 (2016): 49-81.